

FATT ACIDS AND GLYCERIDES OF THE FAT FROM THE SEEDS OF *GARCINIA INDICA* (KOKUM BUTTER).

BY N. L. VIDYARTHI AND C. J. DASA RAO.

Kokum butter, the fat from the seeds of *Garcinia Indica* has been examined in detail for its component fatty acids and glycerides. By the usual method of lead salt separation and ester fractionation, the component fatty acids have been found to be myristic acid (1.2%), palmitic acid (5.3%), stearic acid (52.0%), and oleic acid (41.5%). The component glycerides of the fat have been determined by resolving the fat into two fractions by systematic crystallisation from acetone. The amount of fully saturated glyceride was determined by successive oxidation of the fat. The component glycerides of the fat in round numbers are tristearin (2%), oleo-distearin (59%), di-oleostearin (21%), oleo-palmito-stearin (14%), oleo-dipalmitin (2%) and palmito-di-olein (2%).

The trees of *Garcinia Indica* (N. O., *Guttiferea*) are found in the Western Coast of Madras and Bombay Presidencies. The seeds contain about 20-25% of solid fat known as "Kokum butter". It is used for edible as well as for some medicinal purpose. The indigeneous process for extracting the fat has been to boil the crushed seed with water and the fat skimmed off from the top. The fat has been examined previously by various workers (Hooper, *Agri. Ledger*, India, 1911-12, p. 122; Jamieson, "Vegetable Oils and Fats," p. 76; Bolton, "Oils, Fats and Fatty Foods," 1928, p. 259-61). Heise (*Tropenpflanzer*, 1897, 1, 10) studied the composition of the glycerides by fractional crystallisation of the fat. According to his observations the fat consists mainly of β oleo- $\alpha\alpha'$ -distearin. No other glyceride has been reported in this fat. The glyceride composition of the fat has not been examined by anybody, since then. Heise (*loc. cit.*) examined the fat from the seeds of *Allanblackia Stuhlmanni*, one of the species of the same botanical order and found that this fat as well had oleo-distearin as the chief glyceride. Hilditch and Saletore (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1931, 50, 468 r) found that this fat consists of about 70% oleo-distearin, which is the major component glyceride and it also contains 2% of fully saturated glyceride (tristearin) and about 28% of dioleo-monosaturated glycerides. It is probable that the fat from *Garcinia Indica* contains some other glycerides in addition to oleo-distearin.

Recently a number of investigators have adopted different methods for the study of the glyceride composition of various fats (Amberger and Bauch, *Z. Unters. Nahr. Genussm.*, 1924, 48, 371; Hilditch and Lea, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 3106; Lewkowitch, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1933, 52, 236 r; Hilditch

and Ichaporina, *ibid.*, 1938, 57, 44) and it is possible now to find out the composition of the glycerides with better accuracy.

In the present communication the component fatty acids and the glycerides of the fat from *Garcinia Indica* are being recorded. The composition of the fatty acids has been determined by the usual method of separation of the solid and liquid acids (Twitchell, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806) and fractionation of their esters. The composition of the glycerides has been determined by the method recently adopted by Hilditch and co-workers (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1938, 57, 44 and subsequent papers) for the fats of fruit-coated seeds.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The fat of *Garcinia Indica* was obtained by extraction of the crushed seeds with carbon tetrachloride. 5 Kg. of the seed gave 1.155 g. of solid fat (23.1% on the seed), a bit dark in colour. The chemical and physical constants of the fat are given in Table I, along with those observed by the other workers.

TABLE I.

	Hooper.	Jamieson.	Bolton.	Present workers.
Sp. gravity at 40°	0.895	—	—	0.899
*Refrac. Index at 40°	—	1.4565-1.4575	1.4564	1.4571
M.p.	41-45°	40-43°	34°	39.40°
Sapon. value	186-191	187-191	191.9	189.2
Iodine value (Wijs)	25-34	25-36	36.1	36.7
Free fatty acid in % as oleic acid	—	—	9.7	7.8
Non-saponifiable	—	2.3%	2.3%	1.2%

Composition of the Fatty Acids.—The fat was saponified and liberated fatty acids were resolved into solid and liquid acids by lead salt and alcohol method (Twitchell, *loc. cit.*). The methyl esters of both these fractions were fractionated and the individual acids were identified by their melting points and mixed melting points with authentic samples.

* Calculated from Butyro-refractometer reading.

The low boiling fraction of the liquid acid gave an acid (m.p. 53°) when the oxidation product, with alkaline permanganate in the cold (Lapworth and Mottram, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1698) was extracted with low boiling petrol. There was no depression in the melting point when mixed with pure myristic acid. Palmitic acid (m.p. 62°) and stearic acid (m.p. 72°) were obtained from the various fractions of the solid acids. The oxidation of the liquid fractions gave dihydroxystearic acid, m.p. 130° either alone or mixed with an authentic sample of $\Delta^{9:10}$ -dihydroxystearic acid.

From these observations and the fractionation data, the component fatty acids of the fat have been calculated as shown in Table II.

TABLE II.

Acids.	Liquid (43%).	Solid (57%).	Total (100).	% On non-sap. free acids.	
				By wt.	Mol %.
Myristic acid	1.15	—	1.15	1.2	1.5
Palmitic acid	1.74	3.5	5.24	5.3	5.8
Stearic acid	—	51.63	51.63	52.0	51.4
Oleic acid	39.28	1.72	41.00	41.5	41.3
Linoleic acid	0.17	—	0.17	Trace	Trace
Non-saponifiables	0.68	0.12	0.8	—	—

Composition of the Glycerides.—The fat was rendered neutral by heating with an excess of sodium carbonate solution and the neutral fat was used for glyceride determination.

Fully Saturated Glyceride.—The neutral fat (102 g.), after repeated oxidation with potassium permanganate in acetone solution (Hilditch and Lea, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 3106) gave 1.5 g. of a neutral product of fully saturated glyceride having a saponification equivalent of 297.3 and iodine value nil. On crystallisation from ether at 0°, it melted at 69.8°. So this 1.47% of glyceride is mainly tristearin. There might be small quantity of palmito-distearin but the quantity is too small for any further separation or any quantitative estimation.

Examination of the Mixed Glycerides obtained by Crystallisation from Acetone.—The neutral fat (472 g.) was systematically crystallised from dry acetone at about 0°. Two fractions, one least soluble in acetone (A) and the other (B) most soluble were obtained. The component fatty acids of

these fractions were determined by ester fractionations. The results are given in Tables III and IV.

TABLE III.

	A.	B.	Total.
Weight (in g.)	337.8	134.2	472.0
Sapon. equivalent	259.9	294.4	—
Iodine value	29.8	52.5	—
Glyceride by weight %	71.6	28.4	100.0
Molecular %	71.5	28.5	100.0

TABLE IV.

	Composition weight %				Composition mol. %	
	5.7	9.2	6.7	6.3	9.93	7.3
Palmitic acid	5.7	9.2	6.7	6.3	9.93	7.3
Stearic	60.9	29.5	52.0	60.36	28.80	41.0
Oleic	33.4	61.3	41.3	33.34	61.15	51.7

The palmitic acid contains the small amount of myristic acid and the oleic a trace of linoleic acid.

Both these fractions (A and B) were hydrogenated with nickel catalyst suspended on kieselguhr and the fully hydrogenated products (A—I. V., 1.4 and B—I. V., 2.7) were crystallised from ether, and thus the amount of tristearin of the fully hydrogenated fractions was determined. Tristearin (81.2 mol. %) from A and 83.5 mol. % from B were obtained.

TABLE V.

Fractionation of esters of solid acids at 2 mm. pressure.

Fractions.	B. p.	Wt.	Sapon. equiv.	Iodine value.
S ₁	70-140°	30.0 g.	290.6	3.52
S ₂	140-142°	42	299.7	2.68
S ₃	145-150°	26.5	299.3	2.22
S ₄	150°	17	299.8	2.15
S ₅	150-155°*	9.5	300.0	1.93
S ₆	155°	23.0	299.3	2.00
Residue S	—	18.5	299.6	2.94
		Total 166.5 g		

*Low vacuum,

The glyceride composition of the fat from *Garcinia Indica* calculated from the above observations are given in Table IV.

TABLE VI.

The molecular % of the fatty acids.

	A.	B.	Total.
Mol. %	71.5	28.5	100.0
Palmitic acid	4.5	2.8	7.3
Stearic acid	43.5	8.2	51.7
Oleic acid	23.5	17.5	41.0

Component of glycerides (Mol. %)

Tri-C ₁₈ -glyceride	58.0	23.8	81.8
Fully saturated glyceride			
Tri-C ₁₈ (Tristearin)	1.5	—	1.5
Mono-oleo-disaturated glycerides			
Oleo-distearin	56.1	1.8	57.9
Oleo-palmitostearin	13.5	1.3	14.8
Oleo-dipalmitin	—	1.6	1.6
Dioleo-monosaturated glyceride			
Dioleo stearin	0.4	21.0	21.4
Palmito-diolein	—	1.8	1.8
Tri-unsaturated	—	1.0	1.0

There might be a very small amount of tri-unsaturated glyceride but it could not be more than 1% because the molecular % of oleic acid on the total acid is only about 41%.

The following considerations have been applied for the calculation of the data given in Table VI.

Fraction A.—The fully saturated glyceride, tristearin being most insoluble will remain in this fraction along with the oleo-distearin. Most of oleo-palmitostearin, being sparingly soluble in acetone at low temperature will also be found in this fraction.

Fraction B.—This fraction will consist mainly of di-unsaturated glycerides, with a small quantity of di-saturated glycerides. Any tri-unsaturated glyceride being very much soluble in acetone should come to this fraction, but from the component acids no evidence has been found for its presence in this fraction.

In round figures, the fat from Kokum butter contains tristearin (2.0%) oleo-dipalmitin (2.0%), palmito-diolein (2.0%), oleo-distearin (59.0%), dioleo-stearin (21.0%) and about 14.0% of oleo-palmitostearin. Oleo-distearin and dioleo-stearin are the major component of glycerides of this fat.

Borneo tallow and cocoa butter are of special technical interest because the latter is used as a confectionary fat, and the former has often been proposed as a substituent for the latter. The glycerides of these fats are compared here with those of Kokum butter.

TABLE VII.

	Borneo tallow.	Cocoa butter.	Kokum butter.
Oleo-distearin	40	19	59
Oleo-palmitostearin	31	52	14
Stearo-diolein	13	12	21
Palmito-diolein	3	9	2
Oleo-dipalmitin	8	6	2
Fully saturated glyceride	5	2	2
M. p.	33-37°	32-34°	38-39° (Refined fat)

Kokum butter contains very small percentage of palmitic acid (only about 6.7%), whereas cocoa butter has 23.2% and Borneo tallow 18%. Although the percentage of fully saturated glyceride is low, in case of Kokum butter, the high percentage of oleo-distearin tends to make it a harder fat than both Borneo tallow and cocoa butter. Kokum butter, which has not been industrially much utilised, will prove to be a very good fat for confectionary. The refined and deodourised fat has a perfect white colour, and it does not possess any odour and can be compared to a high class hydrogenated fat.